

Prevalence of Coccidiosis in some Selected Poultry Farms in Sokoto, Nigeria

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The study was carried out to determine the prevalence of coccidiosis in some poultry farms in Sokoto metropolis and anticoccidial agents in use for its prevention and control. A total of 380 fecal samples were analyzed using formol ether concentration technique for the detection of *Eimeria* oocysts from 27 randomly selected poultry farms in Sokoto metropolis. Also a structured questionnaire was administered to the respective farms to assess their knowledge and previous experience with coccidiosis outbreak. It was observed that the prevalence of coccidiosis in the study area was 36.84% in which 19.73% and 17.11% of the prevalence were in broilers and layers respectively. Highest Prevalence (29.73%) was observed in chickens raised under deep litter system, while 7.11% prevalence was in chicken raised under battery cage system. A reduction in prevalence was observed among the farms using combination of anticoccidials. No previous vaccination against coccidiosis was given in all the farms visited. Analysis of the questionnaire showed a 55.5% of coccidiosis previous outbreak among the farms visited. Factors such as position of the feeders, sanitary condition of the farms, feed source, and age of the birds affect the prevalence of the disease. It was observed that the prevalence was higher (40.7%) in farms with low feeders' placement than in those with their feeders high above the ground (14.8%). The sanitary condition of the farms was also found to affect the prevalence of the disease among the farms and present the following prevalences; 29.6%, 14.8% and 11.1% for satisfactory, poor and good sanitary assessments respectively. The farms that use both commercial and compounded feed had 7.4% prevalence while 33.3% and 14.8% were observed in farms that use only commercial and compounded respectively. Layers at older age (≥ 30 weeks) had highest prevalence (22.2%) those at growers stage (11-20 weeks) had 3.7% while layers at younger age (1-10 weeks) had least prevalence (3.7%). Broilers at the age of 1-5 weeks had higher prevalence (18.5%) while those at the age of 6-10 weeks had lower prevalence (7.4). It was recommended that the farms should employ the use of anticoccidial vaccination, combination chemoprophylaxis and also good sanitary practices to curtail economic losses incurred by coccidiosis.

Keywords: Prevalence, Coccidiosis, Sokoto metropolis, poultry farm, *Eimeria* oocyst

INTRODUCTION

Poultry production has been a feature of human society for thousands of years. To ensure that it continues to

make positive and sustainable contributions to stable human society, it is essential that production and marketing are tailored to local conditions and associated value chains, maximise nutrient cycling and efficient utilisation of all products and maintain genetic diversity. Smallholder poultry production has an important role to

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play in feeding the world and, to maximise the benefits, it should be accompanied by improvements to local health services and holistic programs that highlight the links between poultry production, human health and nutrition and sustainable ecosystem services. (EARO, 2000). In developing countries poultry production offers an opportunity to feed the fast growing human population and to provide income for resource poor farmers. Moreover, poultry in many parts of the modern World is considered the chief source of not only cheaper protein of animal origin but also of high quality human food (Getachew, 2004).

Poultry production is carried out throughout the world. In Asia especially Iran, it is distinctively divided into commercial and village enterprise subsector each with its peculiarities (Hadipour *et al.*, 2011). The former comprise of the strains developed on the basis of primary products into parent stocks, layers and broilers each with specialized equipment and management approach (Nnadi and George, 2010). The latter however, consist of indigenous domestic fowl (*Gallus domesticus*) variously referred to as local or rural chicken, backyard poultry, village chicken and or free-range chicken (Hadipour *et al.*, 2013).

Native (village) chickens play an important role in peoples' nutrition due to meat and eggs production. However native chicken production is constrained by many extrinsic factors among which malnutrition, poor management, and absence of biosecurity are outstanding (Hadipour *et al.*, 2013). Losses have also been attributed to limited housing and veterinary care services (Nnadi and George, 2010).

In Kenya, indigenous chickens constitute over 81% of poultry and produce 71% of egg and poultry meat (Sabuni *et al.*, 2010).

The major Nigerian livestock resources consist of 13,885,813 Cattle; 34,453,724 Goat; 22,092,602 Sheep; 3,406,381 Pigs; 104,247,960 poultry (RIM, 1992). From these figures, poultry constitute about 58.72% of the total livestock resources, which indicates the place of poultry sub-sectors in the livestock industry. While overall national increase in poultry production has probably triggered off vigorous research into alternative and cheaper feed resources urgently needed to sustain such growth, there is the need to continually focus attention on the health of the animals in order to realize the full potentials of the industry (Fasami, 1990). Poultry diseases remain one of the major threats to boosting poultry production in Nigeria (Halle *et al.*, 1998; Laseinde, 2002). Parasitic diseases are of particular importance because of their high incidence in poultry occasioned by the tropical environmental conditions under which the farmers operate (Seifert, 1996). Epidemiological studies have established the economic importance of coccidiosis as a major parasitic disease of poultry in Nigeria (Majaro, 2001). The importance of coccidiosis is based on the economic implications of its outbreak in poultry farms

(Majaro, 1980; Barksh, 1989). Coccidiosis in chickens is one of the major problems of poultry industry that is caused by protozoan parasites of genus *Eimeria*. It is considered as one of the most economically important diseases of domestic poultry responsible for significant economic losses to the world-wide poultry industry (McDougald, 2003a; Williams, 1999).

Coccidiosis is the most prevalent disease affecting the US broiler industry. An estimated \$90 million is spent in the US, and over \$3 billion spent worldwide, for coccidiosis control annually. The global impact of coccidiosis due to decreased performance, morbidity and mortality is an estimated \$300 million US dollars. *Coccidia* infect every poultry house worldwide. Eradication is nearly impossible; the parasites are prolific, and capable of developing resistance to antibiotics, chemicals and ionophores. To further complicate the situation, limited industry resources are dedicated to new product development for coccidia control. Therefore, it is beneficial to understand the disease, recognize its impact on birds' health and performance (Keith, 2013).

Sokoto is located in the altitude of 13.0514⁰N and a longitude of 5.2314⁰W (www.travelmath.com/cities/sokoto). Sokoto is in dry Sahel, surrounded by sandy Savannah and isolated hills. Sokoto is, as a whole, a very hot area with annual average temperature of 28.3⁰C. However, maximum daytime temperatures are for most of the year generally less than 40⁰C (104.0⁰F). The warmest months are February to April when daytime temperatures can exceed 45⁰C (113.0⁰F). The rainy season is from June to October during which showers are a daily occurrences. From late October to February, during the cold season, the climate is dominated by a Harmattan wind blowing Sahara dust over the lands. The dust dims the sunlight thereby lowering temperature significantly and also leading to inconvenience of dust everywhere in houses (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/sokoto_state).

The main occupation of the community is farming and animal husbandry. Recently, many people are embarking on poultry production ranging from battery cage, deep liter, backyard to local cage system. However, the extreme climatic condition does not support poultry production as such predisposing them to different management problems and various disease conditions including coccidiosis. Also the rainy period provides the warmth, adequate temperature and humidity required for the sporulation and subsequent infection by protozoan parasites, *Eimeria*. But to alleviate the devastating effects posed by coccidiosis many chemotherapeutic anticoccidial agents were employed to control the disease in poultry farms along with many managerial protocols which prove rewarding. However, eradication has proved impossible and the parasites are found in most commercial poultry houses. Also the use of anticoccidial agents does not rule out the possibility of occurrence of clinical coccidiosis as such many

outbreaks of coccidiosis are encountered (Chapman, 2011). Coccidiosis is an economically important poultry disease that causes significant loss from morbidity, mortality and reduced eggs production and also from cost of treatment, control and prevention. Therefore there is a need for the adequate investigation on the best prevention and control measures that would best curtail the economic loss incurred by the disease. The study also aimed at identifying factors that influence the outbreaks of the disease in the visited farms.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Collection

A total of 380 fecal samples were collected. The samples were collected as soon when they were voided as possible using latex hand gloves which were then packed into polythene bag. Maximum of 20 fecal samples were collected per pen randomly to cover all corners of the pen. A questionnaire was design to access data of the farm on coccidiosis, control measures and other relevant questions the sample of which is attached at the appendix. Immediately samples were collected they were processed (maximum of ten samples per day) while the remaining were preserved in refrigerator at 4°C for maximum of 24hrs. Litter samples were also collected from some of the farms.

Examination of the Samples

Formol ether oocysts concentration technique as described by Cheesbrough (2006) was employed to examine the collected samples. This was chosen because of its rapidity and ability to concentrate wide range of fecal parasites, also because risk of laboratory acquired infection from fecal pathogens is minimized because the organisms are killed by the formalin solution, albeit it has the vice of flammability because of ether or ethyl acetate used and also that the ether is highly volatile.

Formol Ether Concentration Technique

Principle:

In this method, feces are emulsified in formol water, the suspension is strained to remove large fecal particles, ether or ethyl acetate is added and the mixed suspension is centrifuged. Cysts, oocysts, eggs and larvae are fixed and sedimented and the fecal debris is separated in a layer between the ether and formol water. Fecal fat is dissolved in ether.

Method

Using spatula, an approximately 1g (pea-size) of fecal sample was collected into a centrifuge tube which

was then emulsified with 4mls of 10% formol water.

- Then another 4mls of 10% formol water was added and the suspension was mixed well by shaking.
- The suspension was then sieved and then collected into a beaker which was then transferred into polypropylene centrifuge tube.
- Then 4mls of ether was added.
- The tube was then stoppered and then mixed for 1 minute.
- The mixture was then centrifuged at low speed (1000 rpm) for 1minute.
- Then using Pasteur pipette, the column of fluid below the fecal debris and ether was collected and then transferred to another centrifuge tube.
- 10% formol water was then added to the level of 10mls, the mixture was centrifuged at high speed (3000rpm) for 5 minutes.
- The supernatant was removed and the sediment was resuspended by tapping the bottom of the tube.
- The resuspended sediment was then transferred onto a clean grease-free glass slide and was examined by using 10× and 40 × microscope objectives.

RESULTS

Results for *Eimeria* Infection from Samples Collected.

The results showed that the prevalence of *Eimeria* infection in commercial poultry farms in Sokoto metropolis is 36.84% with 19.73% in broilers, and 17.11% of the in layers (Table 1).

It was observed that 29.73% of the prevalence was among chickens under deep litter management system while 7.11% was among the chicken on battery cage system (Table .2). The prevalence of *Eimeria* infections based on the use of anticoccidial agents is presented in table 3.

Results for Prevalence of Coccidiosis Based on Data from Questionnaire.

The data generated using questionnaires were analyzed in two phases i.e. base on the previous experience of the farmers with the disease outbreak, and base on the risk factors that predispose the birds to the infection.

Previous experience of the farmers with the disease outbreak, the result showed that there was 55.5% coccidiosis outbreak previously among the farms visited, in which, 25.92% was in broilers and 29.63% was in layers (Table 4.2.1). It also showed that there was 44.4% of the prevalence in birds on deep litter and 11.1% in birds on battery cage (Table 2).

Sanitary condition of the farms visited, the farms were graded as being satisfactory, poor and good. It was observed that the prevalence of the disease in farms with good sanitary condition was 11.1% in those with

Table 1: Prevalence of *Eimeria* oocysts infection according to Chicken Type

Chicken type	No. of Farms	Samples Collected	Samples positive	Prevalence (%)
Broilers	11	130	75	19.73
Layers	16	250	65	17.11
Total	27	380	140	36.84

Table 2: Prevalence of *Eimeria* oocysts infection According to Management system.

Management system	No. of Farms	Samples Collected	Samples positive	Prevalence (%)
Deep litter	18	230	113	29.73
Battery cage	9	150	27	7.11
Total	27	380	140	36.84

Table 3: Prevalence of *Eimeria* oocysts infection According to Number of Anticoccidial Agents Used.

No. of Anticc. in use	No. of Farms	Samples Collected	Samples Positive	Prevalence (%)
None	1	30	0	0
One	7	100	61	16.053
Two	10	120	52	13.684
Three	9	130	27	7.1053
Total	27	380	140	36.842

Table 6: Prevalence of Coccidiosis according to chicken type

Chicken Type	No. of Farms visited	No. with previous outbreak	Preval. (%)
Broilers	11	7	25.92
Layers	16	8	29.63
Total	27	15	55.5

Table 7: Prevalence of Coccidiosis according to management system.

Management System	No. of Farms visited	No. with previous outbreak	Preval. (%)
Deep litter	18	12	44.4
Battery cage	9	3	11.11
Total	27	15	55.5

satisfactory condition it was 29.6% while in those with poor sanitary condition it was 14.8% (Table 3).

Positioning of feeders, the prevalence of the disease in farms with feeders positioned low to the ground was 40.7% while it was 14.8% in farms with feeders positioned high above the ground (Table 4).

Feed source to the farms; the prevalence was 33.3% in farms that use commercial feed source, 14.8% in farms that use self-compounded feed while 7.4% of the prevalence was in farms that use both commercial and self-compounded feed (Table 5).

Age of the birds; the prevalence of the disease in farms with broilers between 1-5 weeks of age was 18.5%, and in those between 6-10 weeks of age was 7.4%, while the prevalence of the disease in farms with layers at ages between 1-10 weeks was 3.7, and in those between 10-20 weeks of age was also 3.7 but the prevalence in those with layers 30-52 weeks of age was 22.2% (Table 6).

DISCUSSION

This study shows that there is occurrence of *Eimeria* infection in selected commercial poultry farms sampled within Sokoto metropolis. An overall prevalence of 36.84% was recorded. This is a significantly high and it shows that there is high endemicity of *Eimeria* oocysts infection in the Sokoto commercial poultry farms. The high prevalence observed may be attributed to the management system operated by the farms in which 18 of the farms sampled practice deep litter system of management. This is a significant factor that exposes birds to the infection as suggested by Methusela *et al.*, (2002) and Taylor *et al.*, (2007) that coccidiosis is high in birds on deep litter due to relatively high oocysts accumulation.

The prevalence in deep litter was higher than that of the battery cage management system. This might not be

Table 3: Prevalence of Coccidiosis According to Sanitary Evaluation of the Farms.

Sanitary condition	Existence of coccidiosis	No. of Farms	Preval. (%)
Satisfactory	Yes	8	29.6
Poor	Yes	4	14.8
Good	Yes	3	11.1
Total		15	55.5

Table 4: Prevalence of Coccidiosis according to Positioning of Feeders.

Feeders positioning	Existence of coccidiosis	No. of Farms	Prevalence (%)
High	Yes	4	14.8
Low	Yes	11	40.7
Total		15	55.5

Table 4.2.5: Prevalence of Coccidiosis According to Feed Source.

Feed source	Existence of coccidiosis	No. of Farms	Prevalence (%)
Commercial	Yes	9	33.3
Compounded	Yes	4	14.8
Both	Yes	2	7.4
Total		15	55.5

Table 6: Prevalence of Coccidiosis According to the Age of the Birds.

Chicken type	Age (weeks)	Existence of coccidiosis	No. of Farms	Prevalence (%)
Broilers	1_5	Yes	5	18.5
Broilers	6_10	Yes	2	7.4
Layers	1_10	Yes	1	3.7
Layers	10_20	Yes	1	3.7
Layers	30_52	Yes	6	22.2

unconnected to the fact that, the birds on battery cage system do not have access to sporulated oocysts which might have contaminated the feeds and water in the deep litter management system exposing the birds to *Eimeria* infection.

The prevalence of in *Eimeria* infection was higher in broilers (19.73%) than in layers (17.11%). Jatau *et al.*, (2012) and Etuk *et al.*, (2004) reported contrary to this study. This finding is attributable to the management system operated by the farms visited, whereof, 9 of the layers farms visited were using battery cage system of management.

It was found that the use of anticoccidials reduces the prevalence of infection. However use of a single anticoccidial agent does not have great impact as observed with combination of two or three anticoccidials. The combination chemoprophylaxis significantly controls coccidiosis because in single anticoccidial agent, coccidia may develop resistance. Chapman (2000) stated that use of combination chemoprophylaxis can be used to successfully control coccidiosis. Strikingly a farm using no anticoccidial agent no infection with *Eimeria*, but it was observed that the farm was practicing closed battery

cage system with improved automated management system and this prevent contact with sporulated oocysts.

High prevalence of coccidiosis outbreak (55.5%) was previously observed in farms visited. Severe (44.4%) outbreak of coccidiosis previously occurred in the farms categorized as being poor and satisfactory based on the observed environmental and sanitary conditions. This shows that there is possible acquisition of sporulated oocysts from the environment which leads to the resistance of the oocysts to the environment (Getachew, 2004). The lower morbidity in farms considered with good environmental and sanitary condition is associated with regular cleanliness and washing of waterers and placing of waterers above the ground level. This is a good practice which prevents accumulation of oocysts in drinking water as opposed to that achieved with uncleaned environment. Mcdougald (2003b) stated that coccidiosis depends largely on number of sporulated oocysts ingested.

High prevalence rate was found in farms that practice placing their feeders and drinkers below to the ground. This is due to the fact that the voided oocysts-loaded-feces easily gain access to the feed and water, therefore

contaminating and subsequently infecting other birds.

High prevalence rate was found in farms with commercially sourced feed. This might be due to the storage problem. In which case feed that is stored for long time may get contaminated through handling or by personnel.

The findings in this study shows that coccidiosis have no age limitation. As it was observed in this study that the young broilers (1-5 weeks) have high incidence of coccidiosis (18.5%) while adult broilers (6-10 weeks) have low incidence of coccidiosis (7.4%). Layers at age between 1-12 weeks have least incidence of the disease (7.4%) while those at age between 30-52 weeks of age have highest incidence of the disease with (22.2%). This finding is in support of the report of Julie (1999) that all ages of poultry are susceptible to *Eimeria* infection, but usually resolve itself around 6-8 weeks of age. Similarly, the management system is a strong factor in determination of epidemiology of *Eimeria* infection as it was observed in this study.

It can be concluded that, there is significantly high endemicity of coccidia in Sokoto despite the use of anticoccidial agents and combination chemoprophylaxis significantly reduces the incidence of the disease in farms than single anticoccidial agent. Nevertheless, method of feeding, sanitary practices, feed source, age and management system operated are significant factors that affect the prevalence of the disease in all farms that raise poultry within Sokoto metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that;

- The farms should practice the use of combination chemoprophylaxis for adequate control of coccidiosis in their farms
- The farms should consider employing vaccination against coccidiosis in their farms to ensure adequate control of the disease
- All the commercial poultry farms should consider the use of battery cage system as the best mean to curtail the economic losses incurred by coccidiosis
- Farmers with small-scale poultry business and unable to afford batteries and farms raising only broilers, should consider practicing good and improved environmental practices and should avoid over stoking.

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